

Unraveling dynamic transcriptomic changes in sheep's lactating mammary gland following *Escherichia coli* lipopolysaccharide exposure

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ABSTRACT

Mammary gland infections constitute a significant challenge in dairy sheep, affecting productivity and welfare. Temporal RNA sequencing (RNA-Seq) provide a valuable approach to evaluate the evolution of the host defensive molecular mechanisms triggered by mastitis caused by external agents or events. This study aimed to characterize the transcriptomic response of sheep mammary glands to an intramammary inflammation induced with an *Escherichia coli* LPS inoculation based on RNA-Seq samples generated from milk somatic cells collected at 3 time points: pre-inoculation (0 h), and 6 h and 24 h post-LPS inoculation. The differential expression analyses between the analyzed time points were performed using 2 statistical approaches: one parametric (DESeq2) and one nonparametric (Wilcoxon rank-sum test). The differentially expressed genes (DEG) commonly identified by both approaches encompass 5,872 for the 0 h versus 6 h comparison, 4,063 for the 0 h versus 24 h comparison, and 1,034 for the 6 h versus 24 h comparison. At both 6 and 24 h, transcriptomic data highlighted a significant decrease in the expression of genes linked to metabolic processes crucial for milk protein and lipid synthesis within the mammary gland. Concurrently, increased expression of genes related to the neutrophil attraction was observed for 6 and 24 h, with differences in gene expression between DEG with the highest expression at 6 h, related to T cell activation, type I interferon-mediated signaling pathway, and 24 h, related to cell-cell neutrophil adhesion extravasation or epithelial cell proliferation. In summary, this study reveals how the sheep mammary gland transcriptome responds dynamically to an LPS inoculation, providing a comprehensive understanding of how gene expression patterns evolve over time and shedding light on the molecular mechanisms

driving the initial defensive response of the mammary gland against potential inflammatory challenges.

Key words: sheep, RNA sequencing, time-series, gene expression

INTRODUCTION

In dairy-type flocks, mammary gland infections have an obvious financial significance. Indeed, subclinical mastitis constitutes one of the major problems influencing total productivity in dairy sheep due to the reduction in milk yield, the downgrading of milk quality and the rejection of milk after antibiotic administration (Gelasakis et al., 2015). Regarding treatments, there is an increasing pressure to develop alternative strategies to reduce the use of antibiotics while maintaining udder health, productivity, and animal welfare (Godden et al., 2017). In this sense, understanding the genetic basis and the pathophysiology of host response against mastitis would help to develop appropriate control strategies, and RNA sequencing (RNA-Seq) proves to be a highly efficient approach for investigating the molecular mechanisms tied to the occurrence of diseases. This methodology enables the study of gene expression and function to identify specific transcriptomic changes associated with physiological and pathological processes (Xia et al., 2023). Therefore, a growing number of studies dissect the immune response of the mammary gland to different etiological agents using transcriptomic profiling (Rinaldi et al., 2010; Chopra-Dewasthaly et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2019).

Stimulation by *Escherichia coli* LPS, a primary microbe-associated molecular pattern of this bacterium, has been shown to trigger the innate immune response within the mammary gland of dairy ruminants (Castro-Costa et al., 2014; Pelayo et al., 2023). In recent years, RNA-Seq technology has been applied to study intramammary LPS challenges in dairy cattle to understand the initial steps of a mastitis process (Long et al., 2001; Moyes et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2019). However, fewer studies have been conducted to evaluate the host response to mastitis in

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The list of standard abbreviations for JDS is available at adsa.org/jds-abbreviations-24. Nonstandard abbreviations are available in the Notes.

sheep using RNA-Seq data (Bonnefont et al., 2011; Li et al., 2019).

Mammary gland epithelial cells are the primary point where bacterial infection intersects with mammary immunity. In this initial phase, epithelial cells serve dual roles by acting as a natural barrier against pathogen invasion and initiating the host's earliest immune recognition and response to pathogenic microorganisms (Xia et al., 2023). Furthermore, they play a crucial role in coordinating the expression of downstream immune molecules and the recruitment of leukocytes (neutrophils; Aitken et al., 2011). Most of the RNA-Seq studies analyzing host transcriptomic response to mastitis in ruminants are based on the comparison between healthy and mastitis mammary glands (Chopra-Dewasthaly et al., 2017; Asselstine et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019). However, after intramammary infection, the molecular processes in the mammary glands become intricate, and there is a lack of studies examining the temporal progression of transcriptomic changes. Temporal analyses allow for the observation of changes over time, providing a dynamic understanding of the progression of mastitis. Various RNA sources have been used to study the mammary gland transcriptome during lactation in mammals. The analysis of milk somatic cells (MSC) is the most accessible method compared with invasive approaches (Cánovas et al., 2014), especially when dynamic studies with several sampling time points are required for the same animal (Suárez-Vega et al., 2015).

On these premises, the main objective of this research was to characterize the dynamic transcriptomic response of the sheep lactating mammary gland against an intramammary inflammatory challenge. To this aim, a temporal analysis was performed at 3 time points: before *E. coli* LPS inoculation, and 6 and 24 h after inoculation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethics Statements

All the experimental procedures were approved by the Animal Experimentation and Welfare Subcommittee of the University of León (Reference OEBA-ULE-013-2019) and the corresponding department of the Junta de Castilla y León regional government (Resolution 23/01/2020, Agriculture and Livestock Department, Junta de Castilla y León, Spain). The animals used in this study were handled in strict accordance with good clinical practices, and all efforts were made to minimize suffering.

Animals and Intramammary Inflammatory Challenge

Twelve first-lactation Assaf ewes were used in this study. These sheep were kept in freestall housing at

the Instituto de Ganadería de Montaña in León, Spain. Animals were fed the same rations and endured no water restrictions. To avoid differences due to lactation stage, estrus was synchronized, and ewes were inseminated around 10 mo of age, so lambing was concentrated in a few days. Once lambing, ewes were milked twice daily at approximately 0830 h and 1830 h, in a single-side milking parlor with 10 stalls (DeLaval, Madrid, Spain). At approximately d 150 of their first lactation, the lactating ewes were challenged with an intramammary gland infusion of *E. coli* LPS.

To ensure no signs of subclinical mastitis, 24 h before the LPS challenge, the SCC (number of cells \times 1,000 \times mL⁻¹) was measured for milk samples obtained from each half-udder of the 12 ewes under study in a regional reference laboratory for milk analysis CENSYRA (León, Spain). The half-udder with the lowest SCC value was selected to be challenged with the LPS infusion. Note that the SCC averages (SD) at the 24 h before the LPS challenge sampling point were 120×10^3 (90) cells/mL for the LPS inoculated half-udders and 219×10^3 (287) cells/mL for the contralateral half-udders.

A sterile solution of LPS (10 μ g/mL, ultrapure LPS, Invivogen, Toulouse, France) was prepared in PBS (Life Technologies SAS, Saint Aubin, France) containing 0.1% BSA (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Quentin Fallavier, France). Before the administration of the solution, both glands were manually emptied of milk, and the selected teat was disinfected with a compress impregnated with 70% ethanol. The teat canal of the treated gland was catheterized before injecting 1 mL of the LPS solution. Immediately after injection, the cannula was removed, and the udder was massaged to facilitate diffusion of the solution.

Individual milk samples from both mammary glands of each animal (~50 mL) were collected at the 3 time points studied to measure SCC and evaluate the response to the inoculated LPS. The 3 studied time points around the LPS injection were: healthy udder, which is called "0 h" in the rest of the document (milk sample from the healthy udder collected before LPS inflammatory challenge), and the 6 h and 24 h post LPS inoculation, which will be referred as "6 h" and "24 h." These sampling time points were selected based on the results reported by a previous study in sheep involving an *E. coli* LPS intramammary challenge at the end of lactation (Castro-Costa et al., 2014). Furthermore, rectal temperature measurements were also collected at all 3 points. To analyze the relative importance of these traits (SCC for the LPS half-udder, SCC for the contralateral half-udder, and rectal temperature) throughout the 3 studied time points (0, 6, and 24 h), 3 generalized linear models (GzLM) analyses using the SPSS software (IBM Corp., 2019) were performed. For the RNA-Seq analyses, at the 3 sampling points a second 50-mL tube of individual

milk samples from the inoculated mammary gland was collected from each animal.

RNA Extraction and RNA-Seq

The RNA from MSC was extracted using the protocol previously optimized by our research group and described by Suárez-Vega et al. (2015). Briefly, from each ewe, 50 mL of milk from the inoculated half of the mammary gland was used for RNA extraction. To avoid RNA degradation, before sample collection, the udder was disinfected with povidone iodine, and nipples were cleaned with RNaseZap (Ambion, Austin, TX). A sterile gauze was used to cover the 50-mL RNase-free tubes during collection.

For RNA extraction, MSC were pelleted by centrifugation at $650 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C and in the presence of a final concentration of 0.5 mM of EDTA. Then, the MSC pellet was washed twice with 10 and 2 mL of PBS (pH 7.2 and 0.5 mM EDTA) followed by centrifugation at $650 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C . The RNA extraction was performed using 500 μL of TRIzol according to the manufacturer's instructions (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). The quality of the MSC RNA was evaluated using the RNA Integrity Number (RIN) value in the Agilent Bioanalyzer 2100 (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA). The RIN of the remaining samples ranged between 6.4 and 9 (average RIN = 7.5). Samples that did not meet the quality RIN standards for sequencing were excluded from the study. Consequently, from the 12 ewes included in the study, a total of 28 samples were used for RNA-Seq analyses, with the number of ewes analyzed per time point being 10 ewes (0 h), 8 ewes (6 h), and 10 ewes (24 h). Paired-end libraries were prepared using the Ultra RNA Library Prep Kit (NEBNext). Finally, we sequenced the samples on a Novaseq 6000 (Illumina), according to the manufacturer's instructions at Novogene (Cambridge, UK), to a minimum depth of 30 million paired-end reads, generating stranded paired-end reads of 150 bp. The RNA-Seq data were submitted to the ArrayExpress of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) database under accession numbers E-MTAB-13619 and E-MTAB-13994 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress#>).

RNA-Seq Quality Control, Mapping, and Quantification

The FASTQC program (Andrews et al., 2015) was used to assess the quality of the raw RNA sequences. After the quality control, the samples were mapped against the reference ovine genome assembly (ARS-UI_Ramb_v2.0) available at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) using STAR aligner (v.2.7.6a; Dobin

et al., 2013). The genome index was generated using the `-sjdbOverhang 149` option because the sequences had an average length of 150 bp. The following mapping options were used during the alignment: `-outFilterType BySJout`, to reduce spurious junctions; `-outSAMtype BAM Sorted-ByCoordinate`, to indicate the format of the output file from the mapping step; `-quantMode TranscriptomeSAM`, to obtain the output file for the quantification step with RSEM software. The number of reads mapped to each gene for each sample was quantified using RSEM v.1.3.3 software (Li and Dewey, 2011). In this analysis, the options used were `-bam`, to indicate the input file format; `-no-bam-output` to not generate a bam output; `-estimate-rspd` to estimate the read start position distribution from the data; `-calc-ci`, to calculate 95% credibility intervals and posterior mean estimates; `-seed 12345` to set the seed for the random number generators used to calculate posterior mean estimates and credibility intervals; `-paired-end`, to indicate our RNA-Seq data are paired-end; and `-forward-prob 0` to indicate strand-specific RNA-Seq data.

Gene Expression Quantification and Differential Expression Analyses

After quantification, data from RSEM was imported into the R environment using tximport (Soneson et al., 2015). To categorize the genes with different levels of expression at the 3 time points analyzed (0, 6, and 24 h), expressed genes were classified according to the fragments per kilobase per million reads mapped (FPKM) value into low expressed genes (<10 FPKM), middle expressed genes (≥ 10 to 500 FPKM), and highly expressed genes (≥ 500 FPKM). Moreover, raw counts from the top 500 genes selected by the highest row variance (default DESeq2 R package (v.1.32.0; Love et al., 2014) were normalized and regularized log (rlog) transformed with the same package, and used to perform a principal component analysis (PCA).

The differential gene expression analyses were performed using 2 different methods: a parametric differential expression analysis using the DESeq2 R package (v.1.32.0; Love et al., 2014) and a classical nonparametric Wilcoxon rank-sum test following the pipeline published by Li et al. (2022). First, different pairwise comparisons were performed with DESeq2 software (0 h vs. 6 h; 0 h vs. 24 h; 6 h vs. 24 h), and then, the same contrasts were executed with the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. On one hand, DESeq2 parametric test assumes that, under the null hypothesis, a gene has the same mean under the 2 conditions (Love et al., 2014) whereas nonparametric tests do not consider that assumption and require more replicates to perform as well as other models (Stupnikov et al., 2021). The differentially expressed genes (adjusted

P -value [$pAdjust$] < 0.05 and absolute log₂ fold change ≥ 2) commonly identified by both methodologies for each pairwise comparison, which will be referred from now on as DEG, were considered for further analyses.

Gene Functional Classification: GO Term Enrichment Analysis

The functional mechanisms associated with the DEG identified were evaluated by performing gene ontology (GO) enrichment analyses with the *clusterProfiler* R package (Yu et al., 2012) considering the 3 GO established categories: molecular function (MF), biological process (BP), and cellular component (CC). For these enrichment analyses, the org.Hs.eg.db R database (Carlson, 2019) was used as an annotation reference. The false discovery rate was the method used for multiple testing correction (using the *pAdjustMethod* parameter from the *clusterProfiler* R package), with a minimum cut-off value (*qvalueCutoff*) of 0.05, and with a minimum size of number of genes to be considered in the functional enrichment analysis (*minGSSize*) of 4. Then, to reduce the redundant terms and to identify the most representative GO terms from the list of enriched terms, the ReviGO software (Supek et al., 2011) was used. Briefly, this software applies a multidimensional scaling procedure to initially place the GO terms based on an eigenvalue decomposition of the pairwise distance matrix of the GO terms, followed by a stress minimization step that iteratively enhances the agreement between the terms' closeness and their semantic similarities in the 2-dimensional space. The options used during the execution of the software were: resulting list size of 0.7 (medium), and the P -value as the values associated with the GO terms. The advanced options were removing obsolete GO terms, and the semantic similarity measure used was SimRel (default).

RESULTS

Response to the Intramammary Inflammatory Challenge

After the LPS inoculation, mild signs of local inflammation (redness and pain on palpation) were observed in the LPS-treated half-udder of the ewes analyzed, whereas no signs of local inflammation were observed in the contralateral half-udder. The LPS infusion increased both SCC values (in the untreated and LPS-treated udders) and body temperature, reaching the maximum values at 6 h after inoculation. Briefly, the average value (SD) obtained for SCC at 0, 6, and 24 h was 142.3 (130.2), 559.9 (452.8), and 405.7 (460.5), respectively, for the untreated udder, and 90.6 (45.9), 22,650 (4,533.4), and 20,323.6

(6,159.8) respectively, for the LPS-treated udder. In the case of rectal temperature, the mean values found were 39.2 (0.4), 39.5 (0.6), and 39.2 (0.5) for 0, 6, and 24 h, respectively. The GzLM analysis results showed that only the SCC values (log₁₀-transformed data) of the LPS-treated udder had a highly significant effect over the 3 time points ($P < 0.001$, data not shown).

RNA-Seq Summary Statistics

A total of 28 RNA samples extracted from MSC of 12 ewes were sequenced for 0, 6, and 24 h time points to a minimum of 30 million paired-end reads per sample. The alignment statistics of the RNA-Seq data are shown in Supplemental Table S1 (see Notes). The mean percentage of aligned paired-end reads (\pm SD, also expressed as percentages) to the ovine reference genome (ARS-UI_Ramb_v2.0) were 95.06 (\pm 1.57), 93.81 (\pm 0.86), and 94.74 (\pm 1.24) for the 0-, 6-, and 24-h datasets, respectively.

When evaluating the milk transcriptome of the 3 analyzed time points through a PCA (Figure 1), in the first principal component (PC), which accumulated 56.9% of the variance, the 0 h samples formed one distinct cluster, whereas the 6 h and 24 h samples grouped together in a separate cluster. The second PC accounted for 25.3% of the variance and discriminated between the 2 time points after the LPS inoculation (6 and 24 h).

Gene expression was normalized using the FPKM method. The total number of expressed genes (genes with at least 0.01 FPKM in one sample) was 18,497 genes at 0 h, 16,150 genes at 6 h, and 18,049 genes at 24 h. According to the FPKM value, expressed genes were classified

Figure 1. Principal component analysis (PCA) plot of milk somatic cell transcriptomes from the 3 time points studied in relation to *Escherichia coli* LPS inoculation. Samples before the LPS inoculation are represented in green (0 h), and purple and orange represent 6 h and 24 h after LPS inoculation, respectively. The PCA was generated from the raw counts for the top 500 genes selected by the highest row variance (default DESeq2) of all samples analyzed in this work after being normalized and log-transformed with the DESeq2 package.

Table 1. RNA-Seq gene expression distribution for the 3 time points (0, 6, and 24 h) studied in the present work

Item	Time point		
	0 h	6 h	24 h
Highly expressed genes (≥ 500 FPKM)	129	251	311
Medium expressed genes (≥ 10 FPKM to 500 FPKM)	3,042	2,943	4,663
Lowly expressed genes (< 10 FPKM)	15,326	12,956	13,075
Nonexpressed genes (≤ 0.01)	11,689	14,036	12,137
Total expressed genes	18,497	16,150	18,049

into low expressed genes (< 10 FPKM), middle expressed genes (≥ 10 to 500 FPKM), and highly expressed genes (≥ 500 FPKM; Table 1). A total of 129, 251, and 311 genes were identified as highly expressed at time points 0, 6, and 24 h, respectively. The top 10 genes expressed at each time point are presented in Figure 2. These genes constituted, on average, 69.27%, 35.23%, and 24.99% of total FPKM for the samples at 0, 6, and 24 h, respectively. The profile of the top 10 genes at 0 h showed a considerably increased expression level (involving greater than 40,000 FPKM) for the genes codifying for caseins (*CSN1S1*, *CSN1S2*, *CSN2*, *CSN3* genes) and whey proteins (*PAEP* and *LALBA* genes; Figure 2a). This profile differed completely from the post-LPS inoculation samples (Figure 2b and 2c). Four genes had more than 40,000 FPKM at 6 h (*CXCL8*, *S100A8*, *SRGN*, *LOC101103771*), and only one gene (*CXCL8*) had more than 40,000 FPKM at 24 h. Among the top 10 genes at 6 and 24 h, 6 genes were found in common (*CXCL8*, *SRGN*, *RPS29*, *TMSB10*, *IL1RN*, *SDS*).

Differentially Expressed Genes

Differential gene expression analyses evaluated dynamic RNA-Seq changes in the mammary gland transcriptome in response to the LPS challenge. The differential expression analysis with DESeq2 and Wilcoxon methods, respectively, identified 5,980 and 6,529 genes differentially expressed ($p_{Adjust} < 0.05$ and $|\text{Log}_2 \text{fold change}| \geq 2$) between the 0 h versus 6 h comparison pair, 4,181 and 4,592 genes for the 0 h versus 24 h, and 1,115 and 1,207 genes for the 6 h versus 24 h pair (Table 2). Comparing the results of the 2 methods, the common genes identified for the different comparisons and considered as DEG, were 5,872 DEG for the 0 h versus 6 h, 4,063 DEG for 0 h versus 24 h, and 1,034 DEG for the 6 h versus 24 h comparison pairs (Supplemental Table S2, see Notes).

When comparing the total genes found as DEG between the different pairwise comparisons (0 h vs. 6 h, 0 h vs. 24 h, and 6 h vs. 24 h), 40% of the DEG identified were unique for each time point contrast, and 60% of the DEG were found in common by more than one time point contrast. Thus, we found 1,971 unique DEG between the

0 h versus 6 h comparison pair, 492 between 0 h versus 24 h, and 192 between 6 h versus 24 h. Among the DEG found in common by more than one time point contrast, the following gene sets were defined: set a, all time points commonly identified 320 DEG; set b, 3,155 DEG were found in common between 0 h versus 6 h and 0 h versus 24 h pairs; set c, 426 common DEG were identi-

Figure 2. Bar graph with the top 10 highly expressed genes in milk somatic cells at 0 h before *Escherichia coli* LPS injection (A) and at 6 h (B) and 24 h (C) after LPS injection. The FPKM values are indicated on the x-axis, whereas the genes are represented on the y-axis.

Table 2. Number of differentially expressed genes (DEG) at all possible pairs of time points (0 h vs. 6 h; 0 h vs. 24 h; 6 h vs. 24 h) using the 2 methods studied: DESeq2 as parametric method and Wilcoxon rank-sum test as nonparametric

Method	Time point		
	0 h vs. 6 h	0 h vs. 24 h	6 h vs. 24 h
DESeq2	5,980	4,181	1,115
Wilcoxon rank-sum test	6,529	4,592	1,207
Common DEG between the 2 methods	5,872	4,063	1,034

fied between pairs 0 h versus 6 h and 6 h versus 24 h; and set d, 96 common DEG between 6 h versus 24 h and 0 h versus 24 h pairs (Figure 3).

To evaluate the longitudinal changes in expression of the 60% of the DEG identified by at least 2 of the contrasted time points evaluated, heatmaps for the 4 sets of DEG defined (a, b, c and d) over the 3 time points were plotted (Figure 4). The figure helped us to understand the expression profile of DEG throughout the study. Gene expression was very similar for genes sets a and c, upregulated at 6 h (with a markedly greater expres-

sion) and 24 h compared with 0 h. Regarding set b, the figure showed a clear difference between the upregulated DEG at 6 h and 24 h with respect to 0 h, but in this case, the differences in gene expression found at 6 h and 24 h were less marked. Finally, the last group (d set) showed a group of genes with higher expression at 24 h than at 0 h and 6 h.

Gene Functional Classification: GO Term Enrichment Analysis

For the total of 1,971 noncommon DEG between 0 h and 6 h time point comparisons, 11 GO terms were significantly enriched after redundant reduction with ReviGO ($qvalueCutoff < 0.05$) across the 3 GO established classes: BP (9 terms), MF (0 terms), and CC (2 terms). Of them, tRNA metabolic process ($pAdjust = 1.35 \times 10^{-5}$, 36 genes), mitochondrial gene expression ($pAdjust = 1.35 \times 10^{-5}$, 32 genes), and mitochondrial matrix ($pAdjust = 2.29 \times 10^{-11}$, 75 genes) were the most enriched terms for the upregulated genes at 0 h, and RNA splicing ($pAdjust = 1.02 \times 10^{-8}$, 37 genes), histone H2A ubiquitination ($pAdjust = 6.59 \times 10^{-6}$, 9 genes), regulation of RNA splicing ($pAdjust = 4.08 \times 10^{-6}$, 19 genes), postsynapse to nucleus signaling pathway ($pAdjust = 4.08 \times 10^{-6}$, 6 genes), and spliceosomal complex ($pAdjust = 2.37 \times 10^{-6}$, 20 genes) GO terms, for the upregulated genes at 6 h. No GO terms were found to be significantly enriched for unique DEG found after redundant reduction with ReviGO between the 0 h versus 24 h, nor 6 h versus 24 h contrasts.

Regarding the common DEG among the different time point comparisons, a total of 44, 321, 33, and 26 GO terms for the a, b, c, and d defined groups, respectively, were identified as significantly enriched after redundant reduction with ReviGO (Supplemental Table S3, see Notes). Specifically, from the 44 GO terms identified for group a, 34, 7 and 3 terms classified within the BP, MF and CC GO functional categories, respectively. For the group b, 241 terms belonged to the BP category, 37 to the MF category, and 43 to the CC category. Among the 35 terms enriched for the group c, 27, 2, and 11 were assigned to the BP, MF, and CC. In addition, for the group d, 13 of the terms belonged to the BP category, 2 to the MF category, and 11 to the CC category. Figure 5 illus-

Figure 3. Venn diagram showing the number of differentially expressed genes (DEG) across the time point comparisons for the intramammary inflammatory challenge. The purple circle contains DEG obtained for the contrast between the healthy mammary gland (0 h) and the 6 h after inoculation of the *Escherichia coli* LPS, and the green circle contains the number of DEG obtained in contrast between 0 h and 24 h after LPS inoculation. The yellow circle contains the number of DEG obtained between 6 h and 24 h after LPS inoculation.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the most representative enriched gene ontology (GO) terms highlighted by our functional analysis in relation to the differentially expressed genes (DEG) identified across the intramammary inflammatory challenge. The 4 groups defined are indicated with different colors: red for set a (common DEG at all time points); green for set b (common DEG between healthy mammary gland [0 h] vs. 6 h after *Escherichia coli* LPS inoculation, and 0 h versus 24 h after *E. coli* LPS inoculation time comparisons); yellow for set c (common DEG between 0 h vs. 6 h and 6 h vs. 24 h time comparisons); and purple for set d (common DEG between the 0 h vs. 24 h and 6 h vs. 24 h time comparisons). The different colored arrows correspond to each of the 4 groups defined (a, b, c, and d) and are linked to a summary box where the top 5 enriched GO terms are summarized. In addition, next to each summary box, the expression profile of the differentially expressed genes in each group is represented. The terms within each box are colored (blue and pink) according to the expression profile of the DEG clustered within these terms for each defined group.

most enriched terms for genes upregulated at 0 h and, neutrophil activation ($pAdjust = 6.29 \times 10^{-41}$, 124 genes), neutrophil-mediated immunity ($pAdjust = 1.31 \times 10^{-40}$, 123 genes), secretory granule membrane ($pAdjust = 1.95 \times 10^{-25}$, 77 genes), positive regulation of cell adhesion ($pAdjust = 3.12 \times 10^{-18}$, 81 genes), and positive regulation of cytokine production ($pAdjust = 4.09 \times 10^{-18}$, 82 genes) terms for those upregulated at 6 h. For the dataset c, significant terms were obtained from ReviGO results for 6 h but not for 0 h. However, the DEG upregulated at 0 h were related to the GO term “cell receptor” using *clusterProfiler*. The most enriched terms for genes upregulated at 6 h from ReviGO were response to virus ($pAdjust = 1.85 \times 10^{-7}$, 21 genes), negative regulation of viral process ($pAdjust = 1.31 \times 10^{-6}$, 11 genes), regulation of viral process ($pAdjust = 3.7 \times 10^{-5}$, 13 genes), regulation of BP involved in symbiotic ($pAdjust = 4.10 \times 10^{-5}$, 13 genes), and type I interferon-mediated signaling pathway ($pAdjust = 1.22 \times 10^{-4}$, 9 genes). Finally, for the d dataset, there were no enriched terms at 0 h, but pigment granule ($pAdjust = 9.70 \times 10^{-4}$, 5 genes), melanosome ($pAdjust = 9.70 \times 10^{-4}$, 5 genes), apical part of cell

($pAdjust = 9.70 \times 10^{-4}$, 8 genes), filopodium membrane ($pAdjust = 9.70 \times 10^{-4}$, 3 genes), and basolateral plasma membrane ($pAdjust = 1.07 \times 10^{-3}$, 6 genes) were the most enriched terms for genes upregulated at 24 h of the d dataset.

DISCUSSION

The worldwide impact of mastitis on dairy cattle and dairy sheep production systems is well known due to the high frequency and related costs of this disease (Bergonier et al., 2003; Barkema et al., 2009). Several studies in cattle have used the intramammary *E. coli* LPS inoculation to study the inflammatory reaction of the mammary tissue by RNA-Seq technology (Moyes et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2019), but in dairy sheep, these studies are more limited. This work analyzed the mammary gland transcriptome of dairy Assaf ewes to understand the different biological mechanisms triggered in the mammary gland in response to an experimental LPS inoculation by analyzing RNA-Seq data sets corresponding to 3 time points: pre-inoculation (0 h) and 6 h and 24 h

after LPS inoculation. This type of analysis allows tracking changes in gene expression patterns of the tissue of interest through different time points. Regarding immunological reactions, this temporal perspective reveals the kinetics of the host response, revealing initial, intermediate and late-phase transcriptomic changes. Consequently, monitoring gene expression patterns could provide valuable insights into disease progression and the efficacy of treatment strategies.

It is well known that the primary defense mechanism against inflammatory challenges or against infections at the early stage is leukocyte recruitment to the affected area, which in the case of the mammary gland produces an exponential increase in milk SCC due to leukocyte diapedesis to the mammary tissue (Bochniarz et al., 2017). Our results are consistent with this theory, because we observed a substantial increase in SCC values after LPS inoculation, peaking at 6 h after infection in both treated and untreated udders. In this sense, our results align with earlier research conducted in sheep by Castro-Costa et al. (2014), who observed a significant surge in milk log-SCC following intramammary inflammation caused by LPS, sustaining high levels for up to 72 h postchallenge. Furthermore, in that study the authors highlighted the 6 h post-LPS-inoculation time point as the highest peak for the temperature records obtained for both vaginal and udder skin (Castro-Costa et al., 2014), in agreement with the results obtained here.

At the transcriptomic level, our analyses showed that this cell recruitment is translated into a clear differentiation of the overall transcriptomic profile of MSC between the samples related to the pre- and postinoculation time points, as observed in the PCA analysis (PC1 accumulates 56.9% of the variance). The differences in the cell profile are also reflected in the top 10 genes found as highly expressed at 0, 6, and 24 h. In line with previous studies examining the MSC transcriptome of a healthy mammary gland (Suárez-Vega et al., 2015), our analysis at 0 h revealed that the most predominantly expressed genes were encoding essential components of milk. These included caseins (*CSN2*, *CSN1S1*, *CSN1S2*, *CSN3* genes), whey proteins such as α -LA (*LALBA* gene) and β -LG (*PAEP* gene). Additionally, genes typically expressed in the mammary gland during lactation, such as *GLYCAM1*, were also highly expressed at this stage (Hou et al., 2000; Wickramasinghe et al., 2012; Suárez-Vega et al., 2015). Previous transcriptomic studies in dairy cows evaluating the genetic mechanisms regulating the host response during mastitis hypothesize that as cell populations differ during infection the gene expression of MSC also differs (Asselstine et al., 2019). Herein, the gene expression profile of the top 10 genes changes completely from 0 h to both 6 h and 24 h post-LPS inoculation (Figure 2). The *CXCL8* gene, considered one

of the most potent neutrophil chemoattractants during inflammation (de Oliveira et al., 2013), was the most highly expressed gene at 6 h and 24 h after inoculation, and no genes related to the main milk components were found to be highly expressed at these time points. Some other genes were commonly identified at 6 h and 24 h. Most of these genes (*TMSB10*, *IL1RN*, *SRGN*, *SDS*) were immunity-related genes previously found in studies comparing the proteome/transcriptome of mammary epithelial cells between mastitis and healthy cows or buffaloes (Younis et al., 2016; Asselstine et al., 2019; Tanamati et al., 2020). These findings reinforce that transcriptomic changes reported in this study are related to an increased proportion of inflammatory cells in the 6 h and 24 h milk samples compared with the 0 h.

Regarding the results of the 2 differential expression methodologies applied in this work, we found a higher number of genes differentially expressed for the Wilcoxon rank-sum test than for DESeq2. This agrees with Li et al. (2022), who suggested that when the per-condition sample size exceeds 8, the Wilcoxon rank-sum test achieves comparable or better power than parametric methods. In any case, over 80% of these genes were common to the 2 methods for each contrast, which supports the validity of the results here presented.

Analyzing gene expression dynamics at different time points after inoculation (such as at 6 and 24 h) can help to recognize transient or sustained responses, which might be missed when analyzing a single time point (Schlamp et al., 2021). The 0 h time, representing the healthy lactating mammary gland, serves as a baseline to compare the gene expression changes observed at the subsequent postinoculation time points. In this study, approximately 40% of the genes were found as DEG in a single contrast, so they were unique to the different tested time points. Among these noncommon DEG, we only found significant enriched GO terms after redundant reduction with ReviGO in the contrasts between 0 h and 6 h. This contrast showed the highest number of noncommon DEG (29.6%, see Figure 3). Among the significant GO terms for the 0 h, we generally found terms related to the mitochondria. Energy demand during lactation in the healthy mammary gland highlights the importance of mitochondria as a key metabolic organelle involved in energy production and biosynthesis (Favorit et al., 2021). On the contrary, the terms found enriched at 6 h are related to splicing events, which seems to agree with previous research on dairy cows showing the relevance of alternative splicing events in relation to the host immune response to mastitis (Wang et al., 2016; Asselstine et al., 2022).

It becomes evident that the defense mechanisms of the mammary gland are complex and act at various levels (Katsafadou et al., 2019). Collectively, our work offers a description of how the host immune system responds

to an *E. coli* LPS experimental inoculation through time. The use of high-throughput sequencing methodologies, such as RNA-Seq, for the identification of promising candidate genes associated with mastitis onset and progression, followed by variant detection and validation by functional studies, may lead to improve mastitis resistance in dairy sheep populations in the future through breeding or gene editing approaches (Brajnik and Ogorc, 2023). In this experiment, the majority of the DEG identified (60%) were common for more than one of the contrasts performed. For an easier interpretation of the transcriptome analysis reported here, we have grouped the results for discussion considering the expression profile of the DEG shown in the heatmaps (Figure 4). Following these profiles, DEG can be grouped as follows: (1) Healthy mammary gland DEG (**HealthyMG-DEG**), which correspond to those DEG with the highest expression at 0 h for sets a, b, c, and d (blue pattern of expression in Figure 5); (2) initial inflammatory response DEG (**InitialIR-DEG**), containing DEG of sets a and c with the highest gene expression level at 6 h (pink pattern of expression in Figure 5a and 5c); (3) general inflammation response DEG (**GeneralIR-DEG**), which include DEG of set b with the highest expression at 6 and 24 h (pink pattern of expression in Figure 5b); and (4) late inflammatory response DEG (**LateIR-DEG**), including the upregulated genes at time 24 h of set d (pink pattern of expression in Figure 5d).

Regarding the HealthyMG-DEG, there were 2 expression patterns to highlight. The first one involved DEG whose expression sharply decreased at 6 h, showing a slight recovery by 24 h (blue expression pattern sets a and c). Among these DEG we found milk protein synthesis-related genes (*CSN1S1*, *CSN1S2*, *CSN3*, *LALBA*) and genes associated with milk fat synthesis in dairy ruminants, such as *LPINI*, *PPARA*, *ACACA*, or *ACSS2*. Moreover, among the GO terms enriched concerning these genes, we found organic acid catabolic process, cellular lipid catabolic process, and mitochondrial matrix. All these terms are related to energy production. In dairy cows, it has been estimated that the lactating mammary gland needs 3 times more energy for production than for the animal's maintenance energy requirement (Butler and Smith, 1989). Thus, as stated above, mitochondrial and catabolic pathways support the energetic and substrate demands for milk production (Favorit et al., 2021). The increase of expression of these genes at 24 h could suggest that at this point, there is a slight recovery of milk synthesis, maybe related to a higher number of milk epithelial cells, compared with the 6 h post-LPS inoculation time point. The second gene expression pattern associated with HealthyMG-DEG was that of genes for which the downregulated expression persisted consistently from 6 to 24 h (blue expression pattern set b). Some of these

DEG were related to GO terms involving cell-cell junction organization, and morphogenesis of embryonic epithelium. These GO terms could probably reflect a state of tissue maturity, stability, and functional specialization, where morphogenetic activities are minimized, and the focus shifts to its primary function of milk production and secretion.

It is well known that inflammation is characterized by the recruitment of leukocytes and the largely choreographed release of cytokines (Ernandez and Mayadas, 2009). The significantly enriched GO terms identified for the InitialIR-DEG were related to the first stages of inflammatory and immune responses (pattern recognition receptor signaling pathway, regulation of leukocyte cell-cell adhesion, T cell activation, type I interferon-mediated signaling pathway, response to virus, or cellular response to lipopolysaccharide). At the initial phases of the immune response, local mammary cell populations such as macrophages, dendritic cells, and epithelial cells have pattern recognition receptors (**PRR**), which interact with pathogen-associated molecular patterns and activate downstream signaling pathways, inducing the transcription of proinflammatory cytokines (Wang et al., 2019). The intracellular signaling cascades triggered by these PRR lead to the transcriptional expression of inflammatory mediators that coordinate the elimination of pathogens and infected cells (Takeuchi and Akira, 2010). One of the genes clustered within the PRR signaling pathway was *IFNGR1*. The α subunit of the receptor for interferon- γ (encoded by the *IFNGR1* gene) plays a critical role in ligand binding, receptor trafficking, and signal transduction (Koch et al., 2002). Despite the fact that the type I interferons originally were identified on the basis of their antiviral activity; subsequently, they were recognized to have antiproliferative and immunomodulatory activities, as well as roles in modulating infection by nonviral pathogens (Lazear et al., 2019). Also, in relation to InitialIR-DEG, significant terms related to cellular response to LPS align with the experimental inoculation of LPS conducted in this study. Within this GO term, it is interesting to highlight the enriched gene family of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerases (*PARP*) represented by *PARP9*, *PARP10*, *PARP12*, and *PARP14*, which together elicit regulatory functions that may influence the course of a bacterial infection (Miettinen et al., 2019). This gene family is particularly relevant, because it has been demonstrated that the lack of *PARP* functions causes difficulties in mounting a well-balanced antibacterial immune response, mainly the proinflammatory response (Miettinen et al., 2019). Another key gene for the activation of the proinflammatory response is *SCARB1*. Taban et al. (2023) demonstrated that *SCARB1* is involved in *E. coli* internalization or endocytosis and activation of proinflammatory response via the TLR4 receptor in goat

mammary epithelial cells. Thus, our study corroborates this gene's crucial role in mammary gland innate immunity in small ruminants. *NFKB1B* is another significant gene within InitialIR-DEG associated with host innate and adaptive immune responses (Chapman et al., 2007). Previous studies in sheep reported that the NF- κ B inhibitor complex factors (encoded by *NFKB1B*, among other genes) were upregulated following scab infestation, showing the highest expression levels at 3 h after infestation (Burgess et al., 2010). In addition, among the InitialIR-DEG, we also find significant genes such as *IL10* or *IL4R*, which encode some of the anti-inflammatory interleukins. Anti-inflammatory functions are now known to rest with populations of regulatory cells and can include fully mature, classical Th1 or Th2 cells that produce IL-10 as a negative feedback mechanism to limit their response. So, more than any other cytokine, IL-10 is an essential component of this regulatory response in almost all infections (Couper et al., 2008).

For the GeneralIR-DEG, the enrichment analysis highlighted GO terms related to neutrophil activation, neutrophil-mediated immunity, secretory granule membrane, positive regulation of cell adhesion, or positive regulation of cytokine production. It is reasonable to associate genes related to neutrophil activation and neutrophil-mediated immunity terms with GeneralIR-DEG. Following an inflammatory challenge such as the *E. coli* LPS inoculation described in this study, neutrophils and monocytes are rapidly recruited, often reaching their peak tissue entry rates within 2 to 4 h (Andersson et al., 1992). In addition, it is demonstrated that the high values of SCC associated with clinical and subclinical mastitis in dairy ruminants are mostly made of neutrophils (Haxhijaj et al., 2022). Thus, our results align with the relevance of these gene types in the context of immune response dynamics. Among the genes included in the GeneralIR-DEG group, we would like to highlight the *CXCR2* gene, a specific receptor of IL-8. It is well established that the production of IL-8 is fundamental for the recruitment and activation of polymorphonuclear neutrophils and other inflammatory cells (Williams et al., 2000). Another interesting gene in GeneralIR-DEG is *TLR4*, which plays a crucial role in innate inflammatory responses. *TLR4* codifies for toll-like receptor 4, which recognizes gram-negative bacteria (or their products) and greatly contributes to host defense against invading pathogens (Wei et al., 2019). In this sense, one other DEG in this group was *TRAF6*, which is important for dendritic cell maturation, cytokine production, and T cell stimulatory capacity of dendritic cells in response to toll-like receptor ligands (e.g., LPS; Kobayashi et al., 2004). *ICAM-1*, also included within the GeneralIR-DEG, plays an important role in the transendothelial migration of leukocytes through its expression on vascular endothelium (Sligh et al., 1993).

Finally, for the LateIR-DEG, some of the most relevant BP-enriched GO terms were related to cell-cell neutrophil adhesion extravasation, regulation of leukocyte migration, and vascular endothelial growth factor signaling pathway, or epithelial cell proliferation. Regarding terms related to cell-cell neutrophil adhesion extravasation, the presence of the enriched *CD99* gene is noteworthy, as the function of this gene in the inflammatory response has been extensively studied, and it has been shown to play a relevant role in the transmigration of neutrophils (Lou et al., 2007). In addition, in this group we find some important genes mainly associated with cytokines with anti-inflammatory effects such as *VEGF* (vascular endothelial growth factor), which is a master regulator of vascular homeostasis and angiogenesis and whose main function is to promote vasodilation, angiogenesis, vascular permeability, and homeostasis (Pandey et al., 2018). In this group, we identified one of the members of the *VEGF* family, namely *VEGFB*, which has been proposed to play a role in regulating the vascularization of adult and embryonic tissues, particularly of muscle (Olofsson et al., 1996). The *CCL22* gene, one of the genes involved in chemotaxis or anti-inflammatory response (Gossner and Hassan, 2020), was another of the DEG found within the LateIR-DEG. In relation to this gene, it is known that chemokines are a large family of small, secreted proteins that stimulate cell migration, most notably white blood cells (Hughes and Nibbs, 2018). Genes related to epithelial cell proliferation or growth factor activity, such as *IGF1* or *IL12B*, have also been found in this group. Variants in the receptor of the insulin growth factor protein (coded by the *IGF1* gene) had been previously associated with susceptibility to mastitis in cattle (Sugimoto and Sugimoto, 2012). During mastitis, bacterial factors and host immune reactions contribute to tissue damage, reducing the number of epithelial cells (Zhao and Lacasse, 2008). In addition, the migration of neutrophils into the mammary gland leads to the breakdown of the blood-milk barrier, inducing greater damage of the epithelium, and, in this sense, epithelial cell proliferation is an important process linked to wound healing alongside tissue repair and regeneration. Hence, our findings may suggest that LateIR-DEG could be linked to the beginning of the recovery of the mammary gland epithelia to an inflammatory challenge.

However, additional sampling points (e.g., at 48 and 72 h after LPS inoculation) would be needed to confirm this hypothesis. Overall, this study represents an initial attempt to understand the dynamics of the mammary gland transcriptome during the early stages of an inflammatory challenge, highlighting key biological mechanisms crucial for the mammary gland's defense against external agents or traumatic events. Future transcriptomic profiling may elucidate how these mechanisms relate to the

immune response activated later against different etiological agents. A better understanding of these mechanisms could lead to novel control strategies to reduce the impact of mastitis-related processes on dairy sheep.

CONCLUSIONS

This research contributes valuable insights into the dynamic transcriptomic response occurring in the lactating mammary gland after the experimental inoculation of *E. coli* LPS. At both 6 and 24 h, transcriptomic data highlighted a significant decrease in the expression of genes linked to metabolic processes crucial for milk protein and lipid synthesis within the mammary gland through the downregulation of HealthyMG-DEG. Concurrently, there is an upsurge in the expression of genes associated with neutrophil attraction (GeneralIR-DEG). Furthermore, gene expression differences were also observed between DEG, with the highest expression levels being shown at 6 h (InitialIR-DEG) and 24 h (LateIR-DEG). InitialIR-DEG were associated with GO terms such as pattern recognition receptor signaling pathway, regulation of leukocyte cell-cell adhesion, and T cell activation, highlighting the importance of genes within these terms for the recruitment of leukocytes into the mammary gland. In contrast, at 24 h, a higher expression of genes potentially engaged in tissue repair and preservation became apparent.

NOTES

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riculture and Livestock Department, Junta de Castilla y León, Spain). The authors have not stated any conflicts of interest.

Nonstandard abbreviations used: BP = biological process; CC = cellular component; DEG = differentially expressed genes; FPKM = fragments per kilobase per million reads mapped; GeneralIR-DEG = general inflammation response DEG; GO = gene ontology; GzLM = generalized linear models; HealthyMG-DEG = healthy mammary gland DEG; InitialIR-DEG = initial inflammatory response DEG; LateIR-DEG = late inflammatory response DEG; MF = molecular function; MSC = milk somatic cells; *pAdjust* = adjusted *P*-value; PC = principal component; PCA = principal component analysis; PRR = pattern recognition receptors; RIN = RNA integrity number; RNA-Seq = RNA sequencing.

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